

A Geographical Appraisal of Household Assets in Rural Part of Kolhapur District

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Abstract:

The Kolhapur district is well known for his well agricultural practice; therefore their economic condition is also good. By observing the condition of the household assets where they reside is supports the above statement. Situation is refers to the condition of household assets whether they aren't so good. In the study region 25.8 per cent rural population uses radio for entertainment. The maximum households assets in Shirol (30%), Karvir (30%), Hatkanangle (29.8%), Kagal (28.9%) and Panhala (27.9%) tehsils has radio because there are wide numbers of FM channels present in this area which provides good quality of entertainment whereas remaining all tehsils are lying below than district average of others household assets like Television, Bicycle, Computer, Internet, Two Wheeler, Four Wheeler etc.

Keywords: Radio, Television, Bicycle, Computer, Internet, Two Wheeler, Four Wheeler

Introduction:

The term describes exactly what it sounds like it would an aggregate amount of assets owned by households- individuals and families –as opposed to assets owned by corporations or other organizations. Measuring household assets, and changes in people's assets can be used to predict consumption.

The value of household assets, when viewed in aggregate across large segment of the economy, helps economists judge the strength of the economy. Increases and decreases in household wealth impact on household assets. It means overall all household assets related an economic condition of household (Igor Stefanovici Zergos)

In this paper, the attempt is made to look into the details of household assets in the rural settlements of Kolhapur district. It further attempts to study the Radio, Television, Computer & Vehicle types like these Household Assets as per the sample study of 24 villages in study region.

Study Area:

Kolhapur district is selected as the study area for the present research work. The region lies between 15° 45' and 17° 10' North latitudes, and between 73° 40' and 74° 42' East longitudes. It covers an area of 785 sq.kms, which is 2.49 % of total area of the state. In 2011 population of the region is 3,876,001 which are 3.44 % of the total population of the state whereas 68.26 % of population live in rural area. The district includes 12 tahsils with 23 towns and 1216 villages

Objective:

1. The main objective of the present study is to over view of the household Assets in rural areas of Kolhapur district.

Database & Methodology:

The present study is based on secondary sources of data. The Secondary data was collected from the District Census Handbooks, Statistical Abstracts and socio-economic review of Kolhapur district. The tahsil-wise data was also obtained for detail investigation. The collected data was processed by employed different statistical and cartographic techniques wherever necessary.

Household Assets:

Radio: Radio is widely used mass communication medium and has a great potentiality in dissemination of information as radio signals cover almost entire population. About 97 percent of the population is reached by the radio. Radio being a convenient form of entertainment caters to a large audience. With the advent of transistors this medium hrs reached the

common man in urban and rural areas of India, though the utilization of radio is more among rural elites. It is the most portable of the broadcast media, being accessible at home, in the office, in the car, on the street or beach, virtually everywhere at any time.

In the study region 25.8 per cent rural population uses radio for entertainment. The maximum households in Shirol (30%), Karvir (30%), Hatkanangle (29.8%), Kagal (28.9%) and Panhala (27.9%) tehsils has radio because there are wide numbers of FM channels present in this area which provides good quality of entertainment whereas remaining all tehsils are lying below than district average.

Television: Television is one of the refined and modern indicators of development and radio is replaced by T.V. in most of the households which is more powerful and enjoyable. The difference between the T.V. and Radio is that the former makes the person ideal. In the latter one, one can listen to radio news and can enjoy entertainment program while working. More than 50 per cent rural population possesses TV in the study area.

The highest proportion of households with TV was in Karvir (63.4%) tehsil and closely followed by Hatkanangle (62.4%), Shirol (58.9%), Panhala (53.2%) tehsils while remaining all tehsils are laying below than district average. It is found that the population in the rural region of study region is behind in using of TV in their houses as compare to urban areas in the district.

Communication Facilities:

Now a day there is various types of means of communication is available such as Telephone, Mobile and Internet and in this mobile is the main and cheapest sources of communication. In the study region half of households have mobile facility where as 7.7 per cent houses poses telephone and only 1.2 per cent households has Internet connection.

In the use of telephone maximum households are observed in Bavda (10.5%) followed by Gadhinglaj (10%), Ajra (8.9%), Bhudargad (8.5%), Karvir (8.5%) and Kagal (8.3%) tehsils. Mobile users are more as compare to telephone there are 50.4 per cent households have mobile phone in this Karvir (53.6%) tehsil has highest numbers followed by Hatkanangle (53.5%), Shahuwadi (53.5%), Chandgad (51.6%) and Shirol (50.7%) tehsils while Bavada (36%) tehsil has lowest numbers of households with mobile phones.

Internet is advance source of communication as well as information technology and in the rural region of Kolhapur district only 1.2 per cent households are use internet. Households in Karveer (1.8%) tehsil has highest numbers of internet connections followed by Kagal (1.7%) tehsil because this tehsils are more developed and highest number of educated population is lives here therefore they are user friendly towards to computer as well as internet.

Table No. 1: Availability of Household Assets in rural area of Kolhapur District

Tehsil	Radio	Television	Computer	Internet	Telephone	Mobile	Bicycle	Two Wheeler	Four Wheeler
Shahuwadi	19.5	38	4.9	0.8	6.3	53.5	19.9	15.7	2.9
Panhala	27.9	53.2	5.7	1.3	7.9	49	39.6	33.3	4.2
Hatkanangle	29.8	62.4	5.2	1.3	6.8	53.5	62	33.4	4
Shirol	30	58.9	6	1.2	7.2	50.7	67.2	33.4	4.1
Karvir	30	63.4	5.3	1.8	8.5	53.6	51.2	38.8	5.1
Bavda	25.1	33.9	4.2	1.5	10.5	36	26.5	22.1	3.2
Radhanagari	22.8	46.3	4	0.7	5.7	50.5	31.2	24	3.2
Kagal	28.9	50.2	5.7	1.7	8.3	47.7	52.3	29.7	3.9
Bhudargad	22.7	48	6.1	1	8.5	48.5	32.2	21.6	3.4
Ajra	19.7	47.3	4.5	1.2	8.9	48.7	19.7	16.4	2.4
Gadhinglaj	24.8	48.4	5.5	1.4	10	44.3	43.3	22	3.4
Chandgad	13.1	48.1	4.6	0.9	7.2	51.6	37.3	25.1	2.8
Dist. Avg.	25.8	53.3	5.2	1.2	7.7	50.4	45.6	28.7	3.8

Source: Field Survey

Computer:

Computer is modern tool which is use for many purpose all over the world therefore rural area is not behind in using computers in there households. In the study region more than 5 per cent (5.2 %) households has own computer. The highest proportion is observed in Bhudargad (6.1%) followed by Shirol (6%), Panhala (5.7%), Kagal (5.7%), Gadhinglaj (5.5%) and Karvir (5.3%) tehsils which is above district average while remaining all tehsils are laying below than district average in terms of computers.

Bicycle:

Bicycle is the conveyance or means of transport of a poor person and about more than 45 per cent (45.6%) households were having bicycle. The highest proportion (67.2 %) in Shirol tehsil and followed by Hatkanangle (62%), Karvir (51.2%) and Kagal (52.3%) tehsils which is above district average while remaining all tehsils are laying below than district average in terms of bicycles. Bicycle is the conveyance of poor persons especially in the rural areas rather than in the urban.

Two- Wheeler:

Under the two-wheelers category are motor cycle, scooter, moped, etc. which are two-wheelers as a modern and advanced conveyance of the people. In the study area near about 29 per cent (28.7%) rural households were having two wheelers and more prominently in Karvir (38.8%) tehsil followed by Shirol (33.4%), Hatkanangle (33.4%), Panhala (33.3%) and Kagal (29.7%) tehsils because this tehsils has more urban area which provides Two- wheeler Showrooms and more garages while remaining all tehsils are laying below than district average in terms of Two- wheelers.

Four-Wheeler:

The possession of four-wheeler is the rare case among the rural population. In the study region only 3.8 per cent households were having four wheelers that were mainly tractors which are used in agriculture purpose. The most prominent is Karvir (5.1%) followed by Panhala (4.2%), Shirol (4.1%), Hatkanangle (4%) and Kagal (3.9%) tehsils because this tehsils are highly developed in agriculture as well as industrial developed while remaining all tehsils are laying below than district average in terms of four-wheeler.

All this with evidences proves that the rural households in the study region the condition was moderate which is not poor or nor good. Their kind of low socio -economic condition

needs immediate attention for raising their standard of living.

Conclusion:

Household assets are included radio, television, communication facilities, computers, bicycle, two- wheeler and four-wheelers. In the study region 25.8 per cent rural population uses radio whereas more than 50 per cent rural population possesses T.V. In the study region half of households have mobile facility where as 7.7 per cent houses poses telephone and only 1.2 per cent households are use internet therefore in the study region mobile is the main and cheapest sources of communication. In the study area more than 45 per cent (45.6%) households were having bicycle whereas near about 29 per cent (28.7%) rural households were having two wheelers while only 3.8 per cent households were having four wheelers that were mainly tractors which are used in agriculture purpose.

In recent period computer & Internet is appliance for communication. Particularly in rural area of Kolhapur district there is lack of this appliances.

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